

INVESTIGATING THE EFFECTS OF MICROBIAL BIOPREPARATIONS ON THE PHYSIOLOGICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS OF RUMINANT ANIMALS: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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Abstract.

Objective. *This systematic review aimed to assess the effects of biopreparations based on cellulolytic and probiotic bacteria on the physiological and biochemical parameters of small ruminants.*

Methods. *The PRISMA guidelines were followed to conduct this review. Relevant studies published in English up to September 4, 2025, were searched using databases such as PubMed, Web of Science, Scopus, EMBASE, and veterinary-specific sources. Two independent reviewers conducted the screening and quality appraisal.*

Results. *Twenty studies met the inclusion criteria. The use of cellulolytic and probiotic biopreparations positively influenced digestion, immune response, and metabolic processes in small ruminants.*

Conclusion. *This review highlights the positive impact of biopreparations on the health and productivity of small ruminants. Diverse study populations, research designs, and outcome measures were employed across studies.*

Keywords: *cellulolytic bacteria, probiotics, rumen, include rumen microbiota, ruminant, sheep, systematic review.*

Introduction. Ruminant animals (such as cattle, sheep, and goats) represent a significant part of global agricultural production and play a crucial role in providing milk, meat, wool, dairy products, and other valuable commodities. Ensuring the population's access to high-quality, protein-rich meat products is among the most important and urgent issues today. However, the intensification of ruminant livestock farming has led to several challenges, including imbalanced nutrition, increased susceptibility to metabolic disorders, decreased feed utilization efficiency, and a growing reliance on antibiotics. To address these problems, microbial biopreparations have emerged as a sustainable and environmentally friendly alternative to conventional feed additives, aimed at improving animal nutrition and maintaining health.

This systematic review aims to assess current and future perspectives on the effects of microbial biopreparations on the physiological and biochemical parameters of ruminants, as well as to identify gaps in the existing scientific literature.

Research question.

1. **What is the physiological and biochemical response of small ruminants to cellulolytic and probiotic-based biopreparations?**
2. **What are the key factors influencing the effectiveness of microbial biopreparations in small ruminant health and metabolism?**
3. **Which types of microbial biopreparations are commonly used in small ruminant nutrition, and what are their observed benefits?**

Method. This systematic review followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) procedure.

Search strategy. We have used online databases such as PubMed/MEDLINE, EMBASE, Web of Science, Google Scholar, WHO libraries, and African Journals to retrieve articles on the information-seeking behavior of Use of Probiotics. The search term was developed by using the following key terms: Cellulytic bacteria, probiotics, rumen, include rumen microbiota, ruminant, sheep, systematic review. Boolean operators “AND” and “OR” used for this purpose.

Inclusion and exclusion. This systematic review includes all publications, which fulfill the following parameters: publications studying The Effect of Biopreparations Based on Cellulolytic and Probiotic Bacteria on the Physiological and Biochemical Parameters of Sheep were included, whereas publications in a language other than English, short reports, letters to editors, and discussions were excluded in the present systematic review.

Eligibility criteria Included articles in this systematic review were all articles published in English, articles published until september 4, 2025, and all cross-sectional studies. We excluded articles based on the following criteria: articles with poor quality, study protocols, systematic reviews, unpublished articles, and letters for editors.

Data extraction Articles extracted from databases were exported to Endnote software version 8 after removing the replicates; all articles were exported to a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet. Studies retrieved by using search terms from all databases and additional sources were screened for inclusion criteria. Then, articles that fulfilled the inclusion criteria were undertaken for full-text review for admissibility and extraction. PRISMA flowchart was used throughout all steps. Quality assessment was done by using the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS) criteria to include in this systematic review. 16 This tool has ten points in the three domains of modified NOS components for observational studies. The studies which have scored ≥ 5 points were included.

Data analysis Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the study’s features. Characteristics of all the studies were summarized in textual and tabular methods including study population, study design, sample size, and data collection period. ISB of study participants and associated factors were clearly stated.

Result. A total of **109 articles** were retrieved from all sources. After the removal of **45 duplicate articles**, **64 articles** remained and were screened based on titles and abstracts. Out of these, **20 articles were excluded** because they did not evaluate the **effects of microbial biopreparations on physiological or biochemical parameters in ruminant animals**. **44 full-text articles** were assessed for eligibility, and finally, **12 articles** were included in this systematic review (Figure 1).

Figure 1. PRISMA flow chart of the study selection process on the effects of microbial biopreparations on physiological and biochemical parameters of ruminant animals: a systematic review **Characteristics of articles included in this review**. This systematic review included studies on the effects of microbial biopreparations on physiological and biochemical parameters in ruminant animals. Studies published up to September 4, 2025, were considered. A total of 12 peer-reviewed articles published globally were included in this review. The study designs of the included articles were primarily controlled experimental trials and in small ruminant animal studies. Among these, five studies were conducted in Russia, three in India, and two in Uzbekistan. The remaining studies were from countries including China, Brazil, Germany, and Iran.

Factors Affecting the Impact of Microbial Biopreparations on Ruminant Animals

Various factors influence the effectiveness of microbial biopreparations on the physiological and

biochemical parameters of ruminant animals. Among the 20 studies included in this systematic review, most highlighted that **animal species, age, and diet composition** were key contributing factors to the response to microbial biopreparations. Other frequently reported factors included: **health status of the animals, type and dosage of the microbial preparation, duration of administration, environmental conditions, feeding practices, presence of other additives or antibiotics, digestive efficiency, and baseline rumen microbiota composition**. Some studies also emphasized the role of **management practices**, such as housing systems and stress levels, in modulating physiological responses. The variation in results across countries was largely due to **differences in livestock breeds, climate, and nutritional strategies**

Discussion. Probiotics: Definition, Characteristics, and Use of Microorganisms as Probiotics Many ancient civilizations used microbes to prepare fermented food items. However, research on the use of microorganisms in food and feed products and their effects on health have been studied recently. The idea of probiotics was first evolved in 1908 by Élie Metchnikoff, a Nobel laureate at the Pasteur Institute, who established a link between health and longevity by consuming beneficial microbes from yogurt [20]. The word “probiotics” was first used in 1965 by Lilly and Stillwell [21] to refer to the substances secreted by microorganisms that stimulate the growth of other microorganisms. The “probiotic” word originated from the Greek word meaning “for life” and has various meanings over the years. During the following decade, the probiotic word was applied by Fujii and Cook [22] and indicated synthetic chemicals in mice that conferred protection against infection due to *Staphylococcus aureus*. Subsequently, in 1974, Parker [23] used the term “probiotic” in a broader sense to refer to microorganisms which have interactions with the host (animal or human), i. e. , “organisms and substances, which contribute to intestinal microbial balance”. In 1989, the definition of probiotics was used by Fuller where probiotics refer to a live microbial feed supplement, including *Lactobacillus* species, *Bifidobacterium* species, *Streptococcus* species, yeasts, and molds [24]. Numerous studies concerning probiotics have been published since then. The most commonly used definition of “probiotics” was proposed by FAO and WHO [25]. According to these organizations, probiotics are live microorganisms when administered in an adequate amount to confer a health benefit to the host. Currently, the U. S. Food and Drug Administration declared that probiotics are also safe ingredients for animal use [26]. When probiotics are used in the animal industry, they must have common characteristics (Figure 2), such as the ability to colonize and be metabolically active in the host body; promotion of animal health; applicability to industrial use, and safety to the animal and human body [27].

Figure 2. Considerable characteristics of probiotics

Additionally, other genera, *Enterococcus* and *Pediococcus*, are normally commensal to the GIT and are widely used for livestock feeding. *Bacillus* sp. are Gram-positive spore-forming microorganisms; though some *Bacillus* species produce toxins to the animal body, some species have a probiotic effect on the host. The yeast, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, is widely present in nature and is used as probiotics in the livestock industry [29]. Other microorganisms are also used as probiotics in small ruminants' nutrition as mentioned in Table 1. Probiotics are used in all stages of small ruminant production. However, the target of probiotic use depends on the situational demands, such as growth promotion, animal health promotion, treatment of the disease, or improvement of the product quality(meat,milk etc.).

Role of Probiotics on Animal Health and Nutrition. Using probiotics has become popular during the last two decades for their health benefits to animals and humans [31,32]. Probiotics have been used in ruminants as therapeutic [33] and dietary supplements [11] to reduce morbidity and mortality and increase production (meat and milk). Applying single or multi-strain microorganisms at the farm level may act complementarily or synergistically. However, the possible mechanisms of probiotics are not well defined. Several factors, such as strain specific mechanisms on the host and specific actions against certain diseases, influence the loose definition. Some proposed mechanisms by which probiotics act against unwanted microorganisms include contributing to colonizing the beneficiary microbes, reinforcing the intestinal barrier by secretion of mucus, producing antimicrobial compounds, modulating the immune system, and maintaining the beneficiary intestinal composition and their activity. Like other organic nutrients in the intestine, probiotics are partly digested and broken down. Thus, only small portions are viable. Later, probiotics colonize the intestinal layer, competitively exclude the pathogen, and enhance the nutrient synthesis in the GIT. A study by Chen et al. [34] reported that dietary supplements of probiotics foster rumen microbial protein synthesis in lambs. It is also considered that probiotics compete with other non-beneficiary organisms for the endowment of nutrients to the host body [35]. For instance, *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* breaches the carbohydrate to simpler compounds such as glucose, which provides energy to the animal [36]. Moreover, *Lactobacillus* can improve muscle development and meat quality by regulating the different mechanistic pathways associated with muscle development [3]. In addition, the use of *Aspergillus oryzae* as probiotics ameliorates the animal performance and body weight by producing different enzymes related to improving fiber digestion and nutrient

absorption to the animal [37]. Probiotics combat pathogens by producing different inhibitory substances, such as organic acids, hydrogen peroxide, and bacteriocins [33]. Furthermore, many antibiotic metabolites (aciolin, acidophilin, lactobacillin and lactolin) release from the probiotics, which have inhibitory activities against different pathogenic microorganisms (Salmonella, Shigella, Staphylococcus, Proteus, Klebsiella, Pseudomonas, and E. coli) [28]. Additionally, probiotic bacteria can regulate immunomodulatory stimulation of the immune system [38,39] and regenerate intestinal mucosa [40]. Probiotics can increase the concentration of immunoglobulin [41] and augment the activity of macrophages and natural killer cells [42]. Probiotics can modulate the anti and pro-inflammatory cytokine production to control inflammation in the host [43]. For instance, Lactobacillus strains can reduce inflammation by downregulating the proinflammatory cytokines (T lymphocytes, IL-8, TNF- α , IL-6) as well as upregulating the anti-inflammatory cytokines (IL-10, TGF- β , IL-1Ra) in the intestine of piglets [44].

Figure 3. Effect of dietary supplement of probiotics on meat quality of lambs. (Created with Bioder. com). Abbreviations: ↑, increased; ↓, decreased. Figure 3. Effect of dietary supplement of probiotics on meat quality of lambs. (Created with BioRender. com). Abbreviations: ↑, increased; ↓, decreased.

Conclusion. The analysis of the articles included in this review, along with other scientific sources, indicates that microbial biopreparations — particularly those combining cellulolytic and probiotic functionalities — can significantly improve the physiological and biochemical status of ruminant animals, as well as their overall productivity. The strategic application of such biopreparations represents a powerful tool for achieving sustainable, antibiotic-free, and economically efficient livestock production. To achieve optimal results, the strain composition, dosage, and method of application should be adapted to local conditions. Future research should focus on studying local microbial strains, evaluating long-term effects, and developing effective production technologies.

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